

INDIRECT TRANSLATION: CHALLENGES AND CHANCES FOR A MARKET- ORIENTED TRAINING

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After having briefly recalled the characteristics of indirect translation, such as the use of a pivot language, flexibility, and/or adaptation, but also the use of transposition and modulation, the talk intends to highlight the application of indirect translation across domains like literary translation but also technical and scientific translation.

To mirror the complexity of indirect translation the case of audio description is also included and, last, but not least, the necessary strategic implications, when texts are culturally remote or linguistically distant.

To substantiate the claims made, the talk relies on the help of the knowledge pyramid developed to better render cultural appropriate equivalents and to achieve functional equivalence.